

All plots received 60-10.6-32 kg NPK/ha (urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash).

Correlations were significant between seedling vigor and tiller number at maximum tillering (0.72** and between tiller number and vigor index (0.45*) (see table). Correlations also were significant between seedling vigor and grain yield (0.68**) and vigor index and grain yield (0.48*).

The results suggest genotype interactions with seed rate and with method of sowing. Fertilizer response was uniform.

The performance of transplanted rice in inland valley swamps may be influenced by the interaction of variety, method of sowing, and fertilization and of sowing, seed rate, and fertilization. Yield differences could be related more to variety than to duration or method of sowing. ■

Effect of nursery management techniques on grain yield of some released rice varieties in an inland valley swamp, Sierra Leone, 1988 wet season.

Fertilization	Sowing method	Grain yield (t/ha)						Sowing method	Fertilization
		ROK11		ROK5		ROK10			
		40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²	40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²	40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²		
Without NPK	Row	1.6	1.6	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.4	1.7	1.7
	Random	1.8	1.3	1.9	1.7	1.7	2.0	1.7	
With 40-40-40 kg NPK/ha	Row	2.0	1.9	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.0	2.1	2.1
	Random	1.8	1.7	2.2	2.4	1.9	2.2	2.0	
	Seed rate (mean)	1.8	1.6	2.1	2.1	1.9	1.9		
	Variety (mean)	1.7		2.1		1.9			
	Coefficient of variation							7.2%	
	LSD ^a (P=0.05)	Variety (V)						0.1	
		Seed rate (D)						ns	
		Method of sowing (S)						ns	
		Fertilization (F)						0.1	
		V*D						0.1	
		V*S						0.1	
		V*D*S						0.1	
		V*S*F						0.1	

^a ns = not significant.

Effect of plant spacing on ratoon rice performance

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We studied the effect of three plant spacings on ratooning ability of medium-duration varieties Ponni and Bhavani, in a factorial randomized block design. The crop was transplanted 21 Sep 1986 in sandy clay loam soil fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

The main crop was harvested 110 d after transplanting, leaving 15 cm stubble. Soil between rows was trampled to control weeds and to prune older roots. The ratoon crop was irrigated at 5 cm depth. Harvest was 67 d after ratooning.

Bhavani was significantly superior in growth, yield attributes, and yield in both main and ratoon crops (see table). Spacing significantly affected yield of the main crop but had no significant influence on ratoon yield. However, productive ratoon tillers/m² and ratoon dry matter production were significantly higher with close spacing.

The correlation of plant density with ratoon yield was positive and significant (see figure). ■

Effect of plant spacing on main (M) and ratoon (R) rice crops in Madurai, India.

	Productive tillers (no.)		Dry matter (t/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	M	R	M	R	M	R	M	R
<i>Variety</i>								
Ponni	445	319	10.0	7.2	4.7	1.8	5.6	2.3
Bhavani	469	414	10.7	7.3	5.5	2.8	6.2	3.4
LSD (0.05)	17	10	0.2	0.0	0.02	0.3	0.2	0.3
<i>Spacing</i>								
15* 10 cm	479	407	10.7	7.8	5.2	2.4	6.3	3.0
20* 10 cm	451	363	10.4	7.0	5.0	2.2	5.8	2.8
25* 10 cm	440	330	9.9	6.8	5.0	2.1	5.6	2.7
LSD ^a (0.05)	20	12	0.2	0.1	0.02	ns	0.2	ns

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Relationship between population density and ratoon grain yield. Madurai, India, 1986 wet season.

Effect of seedlings/hill on individual rice plant yield and yield components

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We studied the effects of seedlings/hill in medium-duration, second season irrigated rice variety E Wan 5 in Jul-Oct 1989. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 1-5 seedlings/hill, with 40 seedlings/treatment. Ten hills in the middle of each row were sampled to measure individual plant yield and yield components.